

IMPLEMENTATION OF AN ALGORITHM FOR BINARY CLASSIFICATION OF HANDWRITTEN DIGITS USING SCILAB

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Abstract - This paper addresses the application of the Perceptron, a mathematical model based on a single biological neuron, in the context of handwritten digit classification. Using the Scilab programming environment, the study investigates the effectiveness of the Perceptron as a pattern recognizer in images. The process of creating an algorithm that collects and transforms digit images into matrices to feed the Perceptron model is described, as well as the training and classification phases. The results indicate that the Perceptron, despite being a single-layer neural network and a binary classifier, is capable of achieving satisfactory results in handwritten digit classification, highlighting its potential in pattern recognition tasks.

Keywords: Numerical Method in Scilab; Perceptron Configuration; Neural Network Training; Image Classification; Character Recognition.

INTRODUCTION

The classification of handwritten digits is a fundamental application in computer vision and machine learning, with numerous real-world applications such as character recognition in documents and postal system automation [1], [2], [3], [4]. An example illustrating the potential of this technology lies in the medical field, where image processing, combined with artificial neural network algorithms, is being employed in the diagnosis of pediatric brain cancer [5].

In this paper, we will explore how Scilab and the mathematical model of a single biological neuron can be applied to solve the specific problem of handwritten digit classification. Our goal is to address the problem by emphasizing the primary purpose of the Perceptron, the fundamental unit of artificial neural networks, as an effective pattern recognizer.

The progress of this research will be presented in sections structured as follows: Section II will introduce the development of the work, including the concepts used in coding and the logic behind Scilab programming; Section III will present the results obtained in the execution of the code in five different scenarios, aiming to obtain important metrics for comparative analysis; Section IV will provide the conclusion drawn from the results achieved in Section III.

DEVELOPMENT

The algorithm written in Scilab consists of three functions, which aim to: access the directory containing the image database, collect data from the digit images, and then transform them into matrices to serve as input for the Perceptron model. Training will utilize data provided by the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database (MNIST), generating the classification system and identifying the number presented to the neuron [6]. The MNIST database contains 60,000 images for training and 10,000 images for testing. Fig. 1 is an example of one of the images included in this database.

Fig. 1 - Digit 2 extracted from the database. [6]

The developed system employs a Single-Layer Perceptron (SLP), and this fact limits it to just two sets of digits, as it functions as a binary classifier, meaning it can only have outputs of 1 and -1 or 0 and 1, depending on the employed activation function.

The SLP is a mathematical model of the biological neuron, conceived by Frank Rosenblatt in 1958, and it is considered the simplest configuration of an artificial neural network [7]. The model is represented by the diagram in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 - Diagram illustrating the operation of a SLP.

The system executed in Scilab initially starts a function to obtain the pixels that compose the training images. This is achieved by transforming the image into a matrix, where each element represents the value of a pixel. Since the images have a resolution of

28 x 28 pixels, the SLP will have 784 values as input to analyze, as well as 784 synaptic weights for adjustment. The transformation of the image into a matrix is made possible through the 'imread()' function from the Image Processing and Computer Vision Toolbox (IPCV) [8]. Fig. 3 illustrates digit 2 as a matrix representation.

Fig. 3 - Matrix representation of the image.

In Fig. 3, the number 0 represents the color black, while intermediate values between 0 and 255 represent shades of gray and white. The next step of the algorithm prepares the training matrix, where the 784 values obtained from each image will form a single column. For example, if we want to train on 30 image samples of the number 1, we will obtain a training matrix of size 784 x 30. In addition to preparing the training matrix, the program also initializes a synaptic weights vector of size 784 x 1 with random values between 0 and 1. After this initial setup, the learning rate is defined, which is used to expedite the network's training towards stabilization, with this value specified in the range between 0 and 1 for optimal results.

Since the program employs supervised training, each column of the training matrix is associated with the desired output value of the neural network, and a vector is initialized with the expected output values for each column of the training matrix.

The pseudocode presented in Fig. 4 summarizes the instructions executed by the Scilab program and the synaptic weights adjustment.

Begin [Perceptron Algorithm – Training Phase]

- <1> Get set of training samples $\{x^{(k)}\}$;
- <2> Associate the desired output $\{d^{(k)}\}$ for each sample;
- <3> Initialize vector w with small random values;
- <4> Specify the learning rate $\{n\}$;
- <5> Initialize the epoch counter $\{\text{epoch} \leftarrow 0\}$
- <6> Repeat the instructions:
 - <6.1> error \leftarrow False
 - <6.2> For all training samples $\{x^{(k)}, d^{(k)}\}$, do:
 - <6.2.1> $u \leftarrow w^T \cdot x^{(k)}$;
 - <6.2.2> $y \leftarrow \text{signal}(u)$;
 - <6.2.3> If $y \neq d^{(k)}$
 - <6.2.3.1> Then $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} w \leftarrow w + n \cdot (d^{(k)} - y) \cdot x^{(k)} \\ \text{error} \leftarrow \text{True} \end{array} \right.$
 - <6.3> $\text{epoch} \leftarrow \text{epoch} + 1$;

Until: error \leftarrow False

End [Perceptron Algorithm – Training Phase]

Fig. 4 – Pseudocode of the training phase. [9].

After the adjustment of synaptic weights, the SLP has 'learned' to identify patterns in the images provided during training. To perform the testing, a function was implemented, which takes as a parameter the already adjusted synaptic weight vector from the training phase. A similar approach to the training phase was applied to organize a matrix of test images. The algorithm responsible for image classification is described according to the pseudocode represented in Fig. 5.

Begin {Perceptron Algorithm – Classification Phase}

- <1> Obtain a sample to be classified $\{x\}$;
- <2> Use the adjusted w vector during training;
- <3> Execute the following instructions:
 - <3.1> $u \leftarrow w^T \cdot x$;
 - <3.2> $y \leftarrow \text{signal}(u)$
 - <3.3> If $y = -1$
 - <3.3.1> Then: sample $x \in \{\text{Class A}\}$
 - <3.4> If $y = 1$
 - <3.4.1> Then: sample $x \in \{\text{Class B}\}$

End {Perceptron Algorithm – Classification Phase}

Fig. 5 – Pseudocode of the classification phase. [9].

The algorithm described in Figs. 2, 4, and 5 was implemented in Scilab.

Fig. 6 depicts the training phase executed in the Scilab Console.

Fig. 6 - Execution of the training phase in the Scilab Console.

The variables used during the execution of the training phase in Scilab are displayed in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 - Scilab variable browser.

The variable 'd' is a vector that stores the expected outputs for each image belonging to the 'x_train' matrix, with these related by their index. The variable 'w' is a 785 x 1 vector, containing 784 synaptic weights adjusted after the training execution. There is also the variable 'epoch,' which indicates how many times the weight adjustment instructions had to be repeated during training.

The classification operation performed by Scilab is demonstrated in Fig. 8 (a) and 8 (b).

Fig. 8 (a) - Procedure for classifying the number 3.

Fig. 8 (b) - Procedure for classifying the number 8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All tests were conducted using 100 training samples for each digit to be analyzed. Table I displays five distinct cases, where the necessary epochs for neural network training, execution time, classification errors, and accuracy rate were measured using 30 test samples for each digit, totaling 60 images to be classified in total. A learning rate of 0.1 was also used in all cases. The experiments were conducted on a system equipped with a 3.5GHz Ryzen 3 2200g processor and 16GB of RAM operating at 3000MHz.

Table I - Comparative analysis of training and classification

Digits	Epochs	Time(s)	Errors	Accuracy (%)
1 & 0	3	10.97	0	100
1 & 7	6	8.79	2	96.67
3 & 8	20	9.42	6	90
9 & 8	19	9.95	4	93.33
6 & 8	13	9.90	5	91.67

From the obtained data, it becomes evident that the SLP operates by recognizing patterns in the images. When trained to classify digits with similar patterns, such as 3 and 8, more epochs are required to complete the training, indicating the neural network's difficulty in adjusting to obtain the expected values for each input. Conversely, digits like 0 and 1, which have completely different patterns, complete their training in a few epochs and achieve a high accuracy rate in the classification phase.

CONCLUSION

Despite the limitations faced during the algorithm's development, the classifications turned out as expected, demonstrating how the SLP, as an unique artificial neuron, is capable of binary classification with few examples and still achieve excellent results, as observed in Table I, where accuracies between 90% and 100% were obtained.

As a future perspective, expanding the number of neurons could potentially lead to more precise results in digit identification, with significantly reduced error rates compared to using just one neuron. Furthermore, by adding more neurons, the neural network would be capable of generating multiple outputs, thereby allowing the classification of numbers ranging from zero to nine at once, without the restriction of only two digits at a time.

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